

NUTRI-KNOW

STRUVITE (IT)

GAS LOOP (IT)

RENURE (BE)

SOS_AQUAE
(IT)

POCKETBOER 2
(BE)

FERTICOOP-GO
(ES)

Grass2Algae
(BE)

Manure
Management
Tool (ES)

MOPS (IE)

Slurry
Concentrator
(ES)

Duncannon Blue
Flag Farming (IE)

Biorefinery
Glas (IE)

Exchanging easy-to-understand nutrient management knowledge with farmers

NUTRI-KNOW aims to improve nutrient management practices in agriculture by establishing an ongoing cycle of knowledge exchange for the benefit of both farmers and the environment.

Struvite

Livestock manure and digestate treatment to reduce emissions and produce struvite

STRUVITE operational Group designed and implemented a prototype, a farm-scale system, capable of recovering struvite from agricultural digestate.

Challenge

Producing digestate treated fractions which release less ammonia and greenhouse gas (methane and nitrous oxide) emissions than raw input digestate, particularly during the digestate field application.

Activity

Monitoring the emissions (ammonia, nitrous oxide and methane) from field applications of treated digestate fractions compared to untreated digestate.

Results

The nitrogen emissions (sum of N-ammonia and N-nitrous oxide) generated from the application of the treated digestate to the soil were lower than the untreated digestate:

- reduced by 19% for the treated supernatant fraction due to depleted content of N.
- reduced by 63% for the precipitated fraction, even if rich in nitrogen and phosphorus, thanks to their presence in saline form (struvite).

Emissions evaluation from field.

Follow our journey!

Visit www.nutri-know.eu

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